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Initial definition of the scientific challenges and initial evaluation plan - Optimising magnetically confined plasmas with GENE

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable we first refine the definition of the Grand Challenge that we want to compute with the two codes of the GENE family. Then we analyze the scaling behaviour of both codes and fit an extrapolation model to the performance data that was obtained by running several simulations of a few timesteps of a downscaled problem on MPCDF's Raven computer. In a following step this extrapolation is compared to the Figure of Merit proposed for the project and a gap is defined for GENE and GENE-X. A roadmap with the next steps is sketched.

In addition the current Software Engineering status of the two codes is described with respect to various aspects.

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1 Introduction

To create fusion energy, hydrogen plasmas of more than 100 million degrees are to be confined in strong and suitably shaped toroidal magnetic fields. The so-called energy confinement time is controlled by turbulent heat transport from the centre to the edge. GENE is a gyrokinetic turbulence code that can quantitatively describe the underlying physical processes, and it has been successfully compared to experimental data from existing mid-scale fusion devices numerous times. The big challenge for the worldwide fusion community is to extend such capabilities to next step devices like ITER and DEMO, and GENE is well positioned to pioneer this effort.

Historically, gyrokinetic simulation was first applied to the central region of the plasma, because this represents a somewhat less complex physical system. More recently, however, these efforts have been extended to the very important edge region, which has a large impact on the global energy confinement time. Given that the latter task involves various challenges which cannot be addressed by well established core turbulence codes like GENE, a new gyrokinetic code, called GENE-X, has been developed. GENE-X is able to handle, among other things, open field line regions, interactions between the plasma and the surrounding material walls, and large amplitudes fluctuations. To provide a parameter-free prediction of the energy confinement time of fusion devices, GENE and GENE-X have to work together. It is the goal of the present project to advance both tools to be very performant on emerging exascale supercomputers while working in tandem. A quantitative prediction of the energy confinement time of the international ITER project, currently under construction in Southern France, will be a milestone in theoretical fusion research.

2 Definition of the Scientific Challenge

2.1 Relevance and Physical Background

In order for a fusion plasma consisting of deuterium and tritium to reach a burning state, the product of the central plasma pressure and the energy confinement time has to exceed a threshold provided by the so-called Lawson criterion. The energy confinement time, in turn, is determined by heat losses due to turbulent transport, and the theory of turbulent processes in hot and dilute (and therefore virtually collisionless) fusion plasmas is described by a variant of kinetic theory, namely gyrokinetics.

Given that turbulence is an inherently nonlinear phenomenon involving many degrees of freedom, the gyrokinetic equations – describing the time evolution of the position-velocity space distribution functions for each particle species – have to be solved with the help of supercomputers. Over the last two decades or so, many gyrokinetic codes have been developed, and over the years, their realism has reached a level of maturity which allows the respective simulation results to be compared quantitatively with experimental measurements. The biggest challenge during the 2020's is to take these simulations from an interpretive to a truly predictive capability. And this requires, in particular, the development of new tools for the edge region as well as their coupling to core codes. The GENE/GENE-X setup described above is well suited to pioneer this kind of effort and take theoretical fusion research to a new level. The main goal will be to predict the

global temperature and density profiles of all plasma species without involving tuning parameters.

2.2 Detailed Definition of the Simulation Setup

In the final target runs, we want to do an ab-initio prediction of the temperature and density profiles of the upcoming ITER fusion experiment from the centre to the wall. This will be done according to the following procedure:

1. Run GENE from some initial condition and some initial profiles for the inner core part of the plasma up to $r = 0.9a$ (a being the minor radius). To reach the turbulent phase and get good statistics (mean values, spectra), up to 100000 timesteps are necessary.
2. From the GENE run, get the temperature and density fluxes and put them into the transport solver TANGO to evolve the profiles.
3. Restart GENE with the new profiles.
4. Do this iteration cycle until convergence (we expect 10-20 iterations).
5. Feed the converged profiles for the core part into GENE-X as boundary conditions and do a GENE-X simulation of the edge and SOL region of the plasma with suitable boundary condition at the divertor and wall.

The concrete coupling of the inner profiles to GENE-X is still under investigation to get smooth profiles in the end.

2.2.1 Detailed Simulation Setup for GENE

For the GENE simulations of the core part, we will use the following grid sizes in the five simulations directions:

$N_x \approx 1000$	$N_{k_y} \approx 100$	$N_z = 24 - 32$	$N_{v_{ }} = 32 - 64$	$N_\mu = 24 - 32$
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The ranges come from the fact that we do not exactly know what resolution is needed for these runs and additionally how the topology of the computers will be. For GENE, the number of cores per nodes and also the number of nodes used for a simulation influences the choice of the grid. We need therefore some room in the parameter set to accomplish for the node structure. All simulations are done with two species, electrons and deuterium ions and with electromagnetic effects included. The total number of points multiplies up to roughly 10 billion points (10^{10}).

The simulation box used for GENE will contain the region from 0.1 to 0.9 of the closed flux surface region. We will employ a Landau collision operator for the simulation.

2.2.2 Detailed Simulation Setup for GENE-X

With the independent code GENE-X, we will simulate the turbulence in the edge and the Scrape Off Layer (SOL). GENE-X uses a Cartesian grid in the poloidal RZ-planes and a discrete number of poloidal planes along the toroidal direction. For the planned ITER

runs, we estimate that at least 48 millions points are needed in the poloidal RZ plane and 32 of these poloidal planes are needed to discretize along the toroidal direction. For the velocity space we plan to use ≈ 80 points in v_{\parallel} direction and ≈ 20 in μ direction. With two species as in the GENE case, this multiplies to a total of roughly 5 trillion points ($4.9 \cdot 10^{12}$). The other physical parameters are chosen similar to what we did for GENE.

Comparing the total number of grid points of GENE-X to the one of GENE and taking into account an iteration number of 10-20, we see that GENE-X uses 20-50 times more resources, which shows that GENE-X is the part of the project which is mainly Exascale relevant.

We have to run the simulation long enough to have good statistics in the turbulent phase. For this we expect 50k to 100k time steps.

3 Gap analysis

All the following runs have been performed on the Raven supercomputer of the MPCDF, where one CPU node consists of two Intel Xeon IceLake Platinum 8360Y running at 2.4GHz and a total of 72 cores per node. The interconnect is a Mellanox Infiniband HDR100. For the GPU runs for GENE, the four NVIDIA A100 GPUs of a Raven node are used.

3.1 Downscaling the Target Case

The target cases are naturally too large to do scaling runs or performance evaluation. To make them accessible on a smaller set of resources, we have to scale them down. Ideally this is a weak scaling to keep the local problem size similar to the large envisaged target runs. But even this is not always possible, as the parallelization strategy may be different for different parts of the code. Nonetheless, we use a reduced problem size and find the typical scaling behaviour with doing a limited set of simulations. All of these simulations only encompass a small number of timesteps.

3.1.1 GENE-X

Downscaling for GENE-X is done by a factor of 800-1000 with respect to grid points compared to the target case, namely using 330661 RZ points, 16 poloidal planes, 40 v_{\parallel} points and 10 grid points in μ direction. We still use 2 species to cover the same physics.

3.1.2 GENE

Although the target case of GENE could already be run on 64 Raven GPU nodes, we scaled it down by a factor of 8 to make it cheaper to do the scaling analysis. For this we use

N_x	N_{k_y}	N_z	$N_{v_{\parallel}}$	N_{μ}	N_{σ}
288	48	24	32	24	2

A simulation of this size runs on 4 Raven GPU nodes, using 4 ranks per node (1 MPI rank per GPU) with a runtime of one timestep of roughly half a second (0.47s).

3.2 Initial Performance Analysis

3.2.1 GENE-X

The following profiling runs has been done, where the notation is always "number of points/number of MPI ranks in this direction". Not shown are the N_φ and the species as in both direction we do not use any parallelization. It is known from other work [1] that the scaling is nearly ideal in these directions. Tpt stands for "Time per timestep".

nodes	vpar	mu	Tpt	mem/node	total mem
1	40/1	10/1	812.9	243.1G	243.1G
2	40/1	10/2	450.9	129.4G	258.8G
5	40/1	10/5	223.2	61.4G	307.0G
10	40/1	10/10	141.5	38.7G	387.0G
10	40/2	10/5	141.1	42.5G	425.0G
20	40/4		96.4	32.1G	642.0G
40	40/8		74.6	27.0G	1080G

GENE-X has an included profiling of the main parts of the code which are exchange, static operators, collisions, solution of Ohms law, dynamic operators and the solution of Maxwell's equations. The times per time step of these parts are named as T_{ex} , T_{stat} , T_{coll} , T_{Ohm} , T_{dyn} , T_{Maxwell} , respectively.

Figure 1: Scaling of GENE-X in velocity space with $P_{\text{RZ}} = 72$, $P_\varphi = 1$, $P_\sigma = 1$. First the scaling is done in μ direction (blue shade), then continuing with scaling in v_{\parallel} direction (yellow shade).

The internal profiling is used to analyze the scaling behaviour of the different parts individually. The runtime of a timestep is given by the sum of the individual parts and each of the parts depend the number of gridpoints and the number of processes.

$$T(N_{\text{RZ}}, N_\varphi, N_v, N_\mu, N_\sigma, P_{\text{RZ}}, P_\varphi, P_v, P_\mu, P_\sigma) = T_{\text{ex}} + T_{\text{stat}} + T_{\text{coll}} + T_{\text{Ohm}} + T_{\text{dyn}} + T_{\text{Maxwell}} \quad (1)$$

Each of the part times is fitted against the profiling results to a formula

$$T_{\text{part}} = \alpha_{\text{part}} \prod_i P_i^{-q_{i,\text{part}}}$$

where we assume ideal scaling in φ and σ direction and hence $q_\varphi = 1$ and $q_\sigma = 1$. The processes in RZ direction P_{RZ} is always a full node which is parallelized with OpenMP (or later in the project uses the GPUs on a node), so we use it as constant in this fit formula. Doing the fit, we come to the following results of the fit parameters

part	$q_{v,\text{part}}$	$q_{\mu,\text{part}}$
exc	0.14	0.59
stat	0.95	1.03
coll	0.68	0.48
Ohm	0.13	0.32
dyn	0.96	0.99
Maxwell	0.01	0.02

It can clearly be seen that the scaling of the static and dynamic Vlasov part scales nearly ideal, whereas the field solver with Ohm’s law and Maxwell’s equations do not scale at all. The α_{part} parameters have also been fitted but are just constants and do not influence the scaling behaviour.

3.2.2 GENE

Using the reduced problem from subsection 3.1, we are able to do several runs to get the scaling behaviour. We do the scaling runs in each direction independently. The Figures 2 and 3 show the scaling with the number of processes in v_{\parallel} and μ direction, respectively. The different colors are the five parts of GENE which add up to the total runtime of the Time loop. Initialization and Autotuning is not measured here. The blue line of the Runge-Kutta update can serve as an indication of ideal scaling. It can clearly be seen that the scaling for the right-hand-side computation without the fieldsolver is nearly ideal as are the RK updates, whereas fieldsolver, plasma induction (which is also a kind of fieldsolver) and the collision operators do not scale well with the velocity space directions.

Figure 2: Scaling of GENE-GPU in v_{\parallel} direction with $P_x = P_y = P_\mu = 1$ and $P_z = 4, P_\sigma = 2$

Figure 3: Scaling of GENE-GPU in μ direction with $P_x = P_y = P_v = 1$ and $P_z = 4, P_\sigma = 2$

We can do also the scaling in the radial x direction and along the field line (coordinate z). The results are shown in Figures 4 and 5. For the scaling in the x direction, we find a bad behaviour for the plasma induction. Also fieldsolver and collision operator do not scale too well. In the parallel direction (z), also fieldsolver and collisions are the most problematic ones.

With these results, we can now fit a four 1D models to the parts, one for each scaling direction. This leads to the matrix of scaling exponents shown in Table 1, which reflects the scaling problems of the graphs for the mentioned parts and directions.

	P_x	P_z	P_v	P_w
collisions	-0.50	-0.14	-0.02	-0.17
fieldsolver	-0.31	+0.13	+0.21	-0.51
rhs w/o fs	-0.88	-0.90	-0.75	-0.96
plasma ind.	+0.10	-0.52	-0.08	-0.25
RKupdate	-0.95	-0.96	-0.96	-0.96

Table 1: Scaling exponents of the code parts in the four directions x, z, v_{\parallel} and μ . A value of -1 would be ideal scaling.

3.3 Performance Projection to the Target Case for Exascale

3.3.1 GENE-X

From the results of subsection 3.2.1, we can now extrapolate the runtime of a timestep to Exascale with the following procedure.

1. We start with the given runtime of a timestep of roughly 800s on one Raven node for the reduced problem.
2. Scaling up to the full problem (factor of $\frac{48 \cdot 10^6}{330661} \cdot 8 \approx 1200$ times larger) this would lead to a theoretical runtime per timestep of $800s \cdot 1200 = 960000s$.
3. Now distributing to an Exascale system with roughly 10000 nodes using a distribution of the problem with $P_{\varphi} = 32, P_v = 16, P_{\mu} = 10, P_{\sigma} = 2$ and the formula 1 with the fitted coefficients, we come to 1105s runtime per timestep.
4. To reach Exascale with just 10000 nodes, these nodes have to be very powerful, usually by employing some kind of acceleration. If we have Frontier in mind, 4 AMD GPUs MI250X are used per node. They have in total a bandwidth which is a factor of 40 larger than what a CPU Raven node has. If taken this factor into account and assume an overall speedup of 40 of the timestep runtime, we would come to a runtime of 28s.

Figure 4: Scaling of GENE-GPU in x direction with $P_y = P_v = P_{\mu} = 1$ and $P_z = 4, P_{\sigma} = 2$

Figure 5: Scaling of GENE-GPU in z direction with $P_x = P_y = P_v = 1$ and $P_{\mu} = 4, P_{\sigma} = 2$

Computing the Figure of Merit, which is defined in the proposal to be

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{\text{"Time per timestep"} \cdot \text{"Total memory bandwidth"}}{\text{"FP size"} \cdot \text{"number of grid points"}}$$

with “FP size” the size in bytes of the underlying floating point number (8 for double precision reals, 16 for double precision complex). Inserting the estimated numbers and a total bandwidth for the 10240 Raven CPU nodes of $300\text{GB/s} \cdot 10240 = 3072\text{TB/s}$, we get a FOM of

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{1105\text{s} \cdot 3072\text{TB/s}}{8 \cdot 4.9152 \cdot 10^{12}} = 94919$$

which clearly indicates the gap to the promised FOM of less than 6000. To reach this FOM of roughly 95000 on an accelerated Exascale system like Frontier, we have to reach at least a speedup in runtime similar to the increase in memory bandwidth. In the case of Frontier a GPU port of the code should improve the runtime by a factor of 40 to get the FOM of 95000. To come to the promised FOM, we need another factor of 16 of performance improvement.

3.3.2 GENE

Similarly to GENE-X we do an extrapolation of the performance from the current smaller runs on a smaller resource set to the target simulation on a (near) Exascale system. As we are working with a GPU ported code, it is known that the local problem size should be chosen as big as possible, hence a strong scaling is inherently difficult as this local size decreases by increasing the number of GPUs used. Therefore we first scale up weakly to the full problem size (in x and y) where we use the fitted scaling exponents in x direction rewritten for weak scaling. From 8 nodes on we then use the strong scaling behaviour of Sec. 3.2.2 with the exponents fitted there.

Scaling with the described procedure leads to an extrapolated runtime of 100 timesteps on 4608 Raven GPU nodes of 30s. This translates into a Figure of Merit of

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FOM} &= \frac{\text{"Time per timestep"} \cdot \text{"Total memory bandwidth"}}{\text{"FP size"} \cdot \text{"number of grid points"}} \\ &= \frac{30\text{s}/100 \cdot 4608 \cdot 5100\text{GB/s}}{16 \cdot 1152 \cdot 96 \cdot 24 \cdot 32 \cdot 24 \cdot 2} = 116053 \end{aligned}$$

which is a factor of 19 higher than the proposed FOM of 6000. This is clearly a gap but one also has to take into account that a strong scaling over nearly three orders of magnitude on the GPU is extremely challenging. Usually the performance of a GPU can only be fully exploited if the local problem size is as large as possible, ideally filling the available GPU memory. For a distribution of our target problem on several thousand GPUs this is obviously not the case anymore which explains the drop in efficiency. We still will improve the scaling and performance of the GPU code, but will refrain from scaling up to thousands of GPUs for this problem size. From a physics points of view, it might be necessary to use a finer resolution in the radial direction, hence increasing the number of x points by a factor of 3. Also the resolution in velocity space is at the lower limit. It is therefore reasonable that we are able to do a weak scaling to a larger number of GPUs and start the strong scaling on a higher level and in the end reach a better performance on an Exascale machine.

Figure 6: Extrapolated scaling curve of GENE. First weak scale in x up to the full problem (violet), then from 8 nodes strong scale in v_{\parallel} (black), z (blue) and μ (cyan). The greenish line is the runtime computed from the FOM of the proposal.

4 Roadmap for Development

4.1 Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code

4.1.1 GENE-X

From the scaling findings of section 3.2.1 we see at least one clear bottleneck in performance of GENE-X, the scaling of the field solver with the processes in the velocity space P_v and P_{μ} . At the moment the field solver does not scale at all with these two dimensions which is due to the fact that the field equations are independent of v_{\parallel} , μ and σ and are solved redundantly on all processes in this direction. To overcome this bottleneck, further investigations are needed. One approach is to redistribute the work to use the velocity space processes for the solution. But this would imply a cooperation of the OpenMP parallelized poloidal fieldsolver with the MPI parallelized velocity space, which is a challenge we have to face.

Another point is the usage of GPUs for the operations on one poloidal plane. This is not yet fully implemented but a large speedup is needed to fulfill the promised performance. Work has been started on this part and seems to be promising. There is enough parallelism available to fill all GPUs of a node due to the large number of RZ points, but here the challenge lies in the effective use of multi-GPU nodes.

A last point is the somehow suboptimal velocity space grid with respect to the background temperature. As we have a large temperature difference between inner and outer boundary for the ITER edge case, and we use the same velocity space grid for all regions in the code, we have to make it as fine-resolved as needed for the low-temperature part and going to as large temperatures as needed on the high-temperature part. Taking into account a temperature span of roughly 100 and the translation into thermal velocity ratio

of 10, we are using 10 times too many points on the low temperature side. One remedy of this problem is to use block-structured grids as in the GENE code [2].

Finally, GENE-X is a quite young code and has therefore still a lot of potential for node-level optimization which has to be fully exploited.

4.1.2 GENE

From the findings in Sec. 3.2.2 we see bad scaling exponents for the collisions and the field equations (plasma induction and Maxwell's equations) with velocity space, but also in the z direction. The velocity scaling problem has the same root cause as in the GENE-X case.

We will investigate this bad scaling behaviour and assess the overall code GPU performance to find further bottlenecks.

4.2 Next Steps Planned

4.2.1 GENE-X

The next steps that have to be done in GENE-X are

- Introduce a scaling of the field solvers (Maxwell's equations and Ohm's law) with respect to v_{\parallel} , μ and σ . This can give a performance improvement for the target case on Exascale of $5\times$.
- Port the code to use GPUs and especially make it possible to use multi-GPUs on one node. The gain is difficult to predict, ideally we get a speedup of the ratio of the memory bandwidths, which would not change the FOM but reduces the runtime significantly.
- Introduce block-structured grids in v_{\parallel} and μ . This also does not change the FOM but can lead to a factor of 5-10 less points in velocity space and a similar runtime improvement.
- Further assess the node-level performance of the code and improve it by standard means as loop reordering, chunking, cache optimization, data reuse, etc. The gain is also difficult to predict but in some parts of the code a factor of 2 might be possible.

All of these improvements are independent of each other and can be done in parallel by different people.

4.2.2 GENE

Also for GENE we can define some steps, though not as clear as for GENE-X:

- Analyze and improve the performance and the scaling of the fieldsolver w.r.t. the velocity space and the z direction. This can lead to another factor of 3-4 in total runtime.

- Improve scaling and performance of the collision operator w.r.t. velocity space and the z direction. Expected speedup for the total runtime is only $1.4\times$.
- Improve scaling and performance of the plasma induction w.r.t. v_{\parallel} and x direction. Expected speedup is another factor of $2\times$.
- Fully port the block structured grids (BSG) to GPU and develop a library for the BSG which can be used from GENE-X and GENE
- Assess the GPU port on AMD GPUs and optimize there

5 Software Engineering Status and Plan

Good software engineering practices are of utmost importance for producing good software that can be managed, further developed, and shared.

In this section we describe the current status of software engineering aspects for the code GENE and GENE-X.

5.1 Copyright and license

GENE is issued under a custom made license that allows free modifications of the code, however, the code can only be distributed by the GENE Development Team. There are no changes to the license planned as going to a more liberate one needs consent from all developers.

GENE-X is not yet published. The choice of the license is under discussion.

5.2 Development process and coding standards

GENE is hosted on the gitlab instance of the Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF). There are two repositories, one at <https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/GENE/gene> which can be accessed by all registered users. The other repository at <https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/GENE/gene-dev> is internal and can be accessed by the development team. Only senior members of the GENE Development Team (GDT) can accept merge requests from the developers. Development happens in the `cuda_under_the_hood` branch. Developers fork the main repository, create a merge request from there. This is tested via CI features on several runners and finally merged in by a senior developer.

Removing of old features is not defined, an only loosely defined style guide is available but not enforced technically. As build system we support officially GNU make with handwritten and distributed platform files for relevant computers. A CMake build procedure is under development.

GENE-X is also hosted on the same gitlab instance in the repository <https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/phoenix/genex>. This repository is only accessible by registered users. An extensive review process with at least two additional reviewers beside the author are necessary for accepting a merge request. A coding style guide is available and is not

technically but practically enforced within the code review process. It is also enforced by the Gitlab platform that all tests have to pass and all discussion threads have to be resolved before a merge request can be accepted.

The build system of GENE-X is CMake which also clone and build the prerequisite libraries.

5.3 Bug tracking

For bug tracking, the possibility to create issues in Gitlab is used internally for both codes for the development process. Issues raised from the users are handled via the email support@genecode.org that is forwarded to all senior developers who decide on how to work on this.

5.4 Documentation and user support

GENE contains detailed user documentation, parameters of the input files, build and run instructions, usage of the postprocessing. A description of the algorithm and the implementation is available on a much less detailed level in publications, PhD theses and inside the code. From the code, an automatic documentation is created via the FORD tool (similar to doxygen but usable only for Fortran) in the pages stage of the CI pipeline.

Furthermore, support requests can be sent to support@genecode.org.

GENE-X The algorithm and the code is described in a high-level style in theses and publications. A code based documentation is created in the CI pipelines with the FORD tool.

5.5 Requirements handling

Both codes do not have a structured procedure for the management of requirements. Usually requirements for the extension of the software stem from urgent or envisaged physical questions and are implemented if personal resources are available. New upcoming hardware also makes new investigations possible which lead to the development of the code in this direction. The implementation of new features is then done either by the core development team or the requesting user or developer is guided in doing the additions.

5.6 Continuous integration and Testing

GENE's CI is implemented on the Gitlab platform with the use of Gitlab runners. A build stage and a stage for unit tests are run on shared runners in a cloud installation at MPCDF, integration tests are run on MPCDF compute clusters. Build, unit and a subset of integration tests are trigger by each push to the development branch. On a nightly basis, a larger set of integration tests are run.

As build system we support officially GNU make with hand-written and distributed platform files for relevant computers.

Test coverage is not automatically measured. Tests are done for available compilers, like GNU and Intel. The tests are run on x86_64 systems and for NVIDIA GPUs. Other

test hardware can be integrated by connecting a Gitlab runner on these systems to the main Gitlab instance. AMD GPU tests are possible, but not done regularly. As the tests are run on the runners of each individual developer (in addition to the shared MPCDF runners), in principle each hardware can be tested if a developer has access to the system.

GENE-X also uses the CI features of the Gitlab platform. For each merge request a set of build, unit and regression tests are run for the Intel and GNU compiler suite. Coverage is automatically tested by the Intel and GNU coverage tools. Currently a test coverage of 90.9% is reached in average.

5.7 Release process

Both codes GENE and GENE-X do not have a defined release cycle. Usually new developments are first used by the developers for a while before made public. If a new release is made is decided by the GENE Development Team, led by F. Jenko. The releases are only loosely numbered, there is no defined versioning scheme.

5.8 Deployment

Deployment is done manually for both codes. For a new platform, the first developer or user working on it, has to write the platform dependent makefile or adapt the CMake settings and submit it to the GDT which will merge it in. Building of the code is in the responsibility of the user of the code.

GENE The code depends on the BLAS, LAPACK, ScaLAPACK and FFTW libraries. Optionally it can make use of Petsc, SLEPC and HDF5 for enhanced functionality. Ideally, these libraries are prebuilt optimized on the system and can be used. If not, on systems where the GDT has access, they are built and made available to other GENE users on request. For all libraries, GENE tries to use the most recent ones available on the systems. For the usage of the different GPU systems available, GENE relies on `gtensor`¹, a C++ header library which abstracts the GPUs in a performant way. There exist backends for all current GPU architectures from NVIDIA, AMD and Intel.

GENE-X depends on the PARALLAX library which is also developed at the same institute and usually in parallel to the GENE-X development. New versions are usually adopted as fast as possible. PARALLAX itself depends on some third-party libraries which are included in a working version as submodules or accessible via `github.com`. Updates are done if necessary. Furthermore, GENE-X needs a Fortran compiler which is capable of compiling `OpenACC` or `OpenMP Target` directives to efficient GPU code.

5.9 Deprecation

Removing of old features is not defined formally and decided on a case by case basis by the GDT.

¹<https://github.com/wdmapp/gtensor>

6 Conclusion

As a Grand Challenge of Fusion research, we want to predict the density and temperature profiles of a plasma in the experimental fusion reactor ITER with the codes GENE and GENE-X.

Both codes have been analyzed w.r.t. their scaling behaviour to extrapolate the results of downscaled simulations up to the full target problem on an Exascale computing system. By fitting the performance results of different regions in the code to the scaling model, we could extrapolate and clearly find a gap between what the code at the moment is able to do and what we promised in the proposal.

For GENE a factor of 19 has been found that is needed to reach the proposed FOM. Steps that are necessary to reach this factor in improvement is an optimization of the scaling behaviour for some of the parts, mainly collisions and fieldsolver.

For GENE-X we need beside a performing GPU port also a factor of 16 lower runtime on an Exascale system. Therefore optimizations of the scaling and the runtime performance are envisaged for the project. The next steps have been shown and briefly explained.

In the last section we have described the current status of the codes with respect to Software Engineering aspects.

References

- [1] Dominik Michels. *Development of a high-performance gyrokinetic turbulence code for the edge and scrape-off layer of magnetic confinement fusion devices*. PhD thesis, Technische Universität München, 2021.
- [2] Dennis Jarema. *Efficient Eulerian Gyrokinetic Simulations with Block-Structured Grids*. PhD thesis, Technische Universität München, 2016.